

Resisting Oppression: Feminist Themes in the Play 'Maa bhoomi'

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to examine the feminist themes embedded in the play, Maa Bhoomi, as they relate to the socio-political context of Telangana during the Nizam's rule. The study uses a qualitative approach to reveal its findings. By applying the lens of feminism to the play's representation of oppression against injustice and exploitation, the study illuminates the female characters' challenges and contributions to the revolutionary narrative. Ultimately, the study discusses the broader themes contained within the play, namely women's agency, resilience, transformational journey, gender inequality, enduring oppressive governance, societal struggle against patriarchal norms, collective action and the transition from relying on male protection to fighting oppression.

Keywords: *Maa Bhoomi Play; Land Struggles; Oppression and Exploitation; Female Empowerment*

1. Introduction:

1.1. Contextual Background of 'Maa Bhoomi':

The play "Maa Bhoomi," written by Sunkara Satyanarayana and Vasireddi Bhaskar Rao, stands as a pivotal work inspired by the Telangana Armed Struggle against the oppressive rule of the Nizam (Satyanārāyaṇa & Bhāskar, 1957, p. ii). The play vividly illustrates the struggles and hardships of the landless and oppressed, capturing a broader theme of resistance to injustice and

exploitation (Lal, 2004, p. 359). The play highlights Telangana's armed struggle as a successful revolution, advocating for redistributive justice (Christof-Füchsle & Khan, 2024, p. 485). As a result of its roots in the social and political climate of Telangana, "Maa Bhoomi" channels the collective struggles of farmers and oppressed classes against government oppression and landlordism (Ramaṇa, 1995, p. 100). In an effort to magnify the significance of the Telangana protest against the Nizam's despotism,

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the playwrights seek to magnify the suffering of the oppressed and raise awareness about their plight (Satyanārāyaṇa & Bhāskar, 1957, p. ii ; Rādhākṛṣṇamūrti, 2002, pp. 514-521).

A significant part of the play's content and reception is shaped by the social and political environment of Telangana during its conception. The relentless oppression of Nizam's police and Razakars, marked by raids, imprisonments, and violent suppression of protests, fuels the playwrights' portrayal of heroic struggles and resistance in "Maa Bhoomi" (Rādhākṛṣṇamūrti, 2002, pp. 514-521). This depiction resonates deeply with audiences in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana, leading to the play's widespread popularity with over a thousand performances and an audience of two million within a year (Lal, 2004, p. 359). "Maa Bhoomi" emerges as a symbol of protest against exploitation and gains significant momentum within the broader movement for social change and justice through its realistic portrayal of peasant struggles.

The play Maa Bhoomi stands as a powerful evidence to the intersection of social activism, leftist politics, and cultural expression, and the play resonates with millions of people. Although the play is associated with the struggles of oppressed classes against government oppression and landlordism, its origin also

has a strong connection with leftist politics (Purushotham, 2021, p. 191). With the support of the leftist movement, the play reaches millions of people as a cultural movement. Leaders like P. Sundarayya, M. Basavapunnayya, Ravi Narayana Reddy, and Devulapalli Venkateswara Rao collaborate to organize cultural activities, including showcasing the play "Maa Bhoomi" through Prajapriya Natyamandali in the Telugu-speaking region (Rao, 1990, p. 265). The success of "Maa Bhoomi" brings substantial revenue to the Communist Party in the form of donations from the masses.

A scholar also points out that "Maa Bhoomi" presents Telangana's revolutionary context but does not adequately depict Telangana's village culture or dialect; instead, it focuses on Andhra Pradesh dialect and life (A.K. , 2002, p. 61). This observation can be viewed in two ways: first, even though it does not reflect the Telangana dialect and culture, the play attracts a lot of Telangana people at that time; second, the neglect of Telangana culture raises concerns about the representation of Telangana.

Thus, the play gained immense popularity through numerous performances, reaching millions of people and setting records for its extensive cultural reach within a short period. The play garnered immense popularity with in a short period. The play was performed

very successfully by Praja Natya Mandali and shows were supported by another troupe from Krishna Distric, Andhra Pradesh. The play was performed by 125 branches of Praja Natyamandali, and it was performed over 1000 shows within a year; Khwaja Ahmad Abbas praised that the play made a world record with these many shows (Rao, 1989, p. 117 Rādhākṛṣṇamūrti, 2002, 514-521 Venkaṭēsvararāvu, 1998, p. 14). With over a thousand performances, the play was witnessed by two million people within a year (Lal, 2004, p. 359; Maddukuri, 1958, p. 62). Thus, the play gained immense popularity through numerous performances, reached millions of people, and set records for its extensive cultural reach within a short period.

Maa Bhoomi contributes to the theatre movement and inspires artistic endeavours focused on societal transformation and the pursuit of justice and equality. In Telugu literature and theatre, the legacy of "Maa Bhoomi" has remained profound, influencing subsequent works and discussions regarding socioeconomic and political concerns of the era (Rādhākṛṣṇamūrti, 2002, pp. 514-521). Throughout the Telugu-speaking region, it is influential in the theatre movement, reflecting the Telangana liberation struggle and contributing to the cultural and political landscape (Ramaṇa, 1995, p. 100; Rādhākṛṣṇamūrti, 2002, pp. 514-

521; Christof-Füchsle & Khan, 2024, p. 485). In portraying land struggles and advocating for social activism, "Maa Bhoomi" sparks discussion and inspires artistic endeavours that continue to resonate within the context of broader societal transformation and the pursuit of justice and equality.

2. Methodology

In this research paper, a qualitative approach was used. A feminist perspective was applied to the textual analysis and critical interpretation of the play. As part of this study, the portrayal of female characters was examined in depth, as well as their interactions and contributions within the socio-political context depicted in the play.

One of the researchers directed the play and presented it to the public in order to gain an understanding of its characters, themes, and various elements (Rajkumar, 2019). Following the performance, data was collected informally from the audience in order to gain insight into the characters. In the course of the production, notes were taken based on the actors' responses to the characters and themes. A number of primary sources of data were utilized, including the script of the play, the notes of the actors, and the feedback of spectators. We collected secondary data about the play from various published sources in order to gain an understanding of its performance and historical context.

There were several ways in which the data was analysed. The researchers analysed the play individually, identifying feminist themes such as gender roles, resistance, empowerment, and solidarity through dialogue, setting, plot, and character behaviour. In order to uncover deeper meanings, one researcher rehearsed and performed the play in front of a large audience. Researchers analysed the collected data jointly.

Through the research process, ethical considerations were paramount, especially with regard to sensitive interpretations of gender dynamics and feminist themes within the historical and cultural context of the play. As a result, the researchers avoided essentializing gender roles and instead focused on the complexity and agency of female characters in the play.

This study had a limitation as it relied solely on literary methods, potentially constraining the scope of the selected resources. This limitation could restrict the depth and breadth of the study, leading to an inability to contextualize the play within the historical context of Telangana during the period of the Nizam government and the Telangana Armed Struggle. A thorough literature review was conducted in order to gain a better understanding of this setting.

3. A Feminist Interpretation of 'Maa Bhoomi'

'Maa Bhoomi' provides an opportunity for feminist analysis, highlighting the roles and interactions of women within a patriarchal society. Using this lens, the storyline explores how women challenge established gender norms and contribute significantly to the revolutionary undertones. As part of their participation, Seetha and Kamala decorate icons depicting freedom fighters and revolutionary leaders and sing empowering songs. The actions of Kamala and Seetha indicate their willingness to express their freedom towards revolution. Both of these female characters display an exceptional level of bravery and resiliency. As a result of some of the actions of the characters, traditional gender roles are challenged as well as power dynamics. The female characters play a significant role in inspiring the community and advocating for collective action against oppressive forces. Through their active participation in the revolution, they challenge ingrained gender norms and redefine expectations of traditional society. The actions of women have demonstrated the potential for bringing about social change as a result of their actions. Throughout the play, feminist views emphasize the complex shades of gender relations, emphasizing the essential contribution of female

characters to the discourse on resistance and liberation.

4. Discussion:

4.1. *Characters in the Play*

The characters in the play represent a variety of themes. These characters represent governance dynamics, rural life, social structure, and farmers' struggles. Characters are designed with themes of power, oppression, justice, and community identity in a village setting in Telanagana during the Nizam period.

Veerareddy is the protagonist of the play. His occupation is that of a farmer. Within the feudal structure of the village, Veerareddy fights oppression and social injustice. As a leader, he is courageous and strong-minded. Against oppressive rulers, he leads the Sangham . He is engaged in a battle with Jagannadhareddy. Symbolically, he represents social change and the revolution. In the play, this character emphasizes themes of empowerment, unity, and sacrifice.

Jagannadhareddy is the village leader, locally referred as Deshmukh. He is a symbol of authority, governance, and oppression of feudal landlords. He is responsible for the distribution of land. Symbolizing power, this character is challenged by the rebellion of the common people against his feudal systems. His goal is to suppress revolutionary movements. He exemplifies deep-seated corruption and power. As a

result of his influence, the government oppresses the villagers. The leader misuses his authority and leads to physical attacks and resistance. During the conflict, he ignited violent clashes with the villagers.

Venkatravu is a Patvari and the village's accountant and revenue officer. In the villages, he is usually responsible for maintaining land records, settling land disputes, and collecting taxes. He emphasizes the role of bureaucracy and administration in rural governance. The play portrays him as a loyal subordinate of Jagannadhareddy. In addition, he is witness to Jagannadhareddy's injustice and exploitation. Without questioning Jagannadhareddy's orders, he follows them. Additionally, he appears in the play as an Antagonist. In his interaction with Yellamanda and farmers, he demonstrates inequalities and power dynamics.

Mastan is a member of the Muslim community, but does not follow the elders of his community. He is Jagannadhareddy's lackey. In the village, he exhibits criminal behavior and lawlessness. He reflects the darker aspects of society, where power is often wielded illegally. He is responsible for imposing unjust taxes. He is always instructed to suppress dissent among the villagers. As a result of their involvement with Sangham, he physically assaults villagers. Using intimidation and violence, he maintains

Jagannadhareddy's authority.

Ramudu is a servant of Jagannadhareddy. He is of Mangali descent, an occupational caste of barbers. In the play, he illustrates the challenges faced by lower-caste individuals. Jagannadhareddy exploits him. Jagannadhareddy seized his land. Ramudu hopes to obtain enlightenment and reclaim his lands. As a result of the exploitation of his land and his desire to obtain it back, he is interested in joining the Sangham in order to fight against it. He supports the villagers and the Sangham. He informs the Sangham about Jagannadhareddy's movements.

Yellamanda is a member of the Golla community. The Golla community is primarily engaged in livestock-related occupations. He is passionate about the Sangham. Injustice and corruption are unacceptable to him. As a result of his association with the Sangham, Jagannadhareddy's people physically assault him. Yellamanda remains resolute and joyful despite many oppressions, and he is dedicated to Sangham's principles. By advocating collective resistance and action, he plays a significant role in uniting the village community against exploitation.

Seetha is the wife of Veerareddy. Throughout her family setting, she exemplifies unwavering care and traditional values. Her portrayal symbolizes suppleness and sacrifice.

Her commitment to social change and justice is evident. Her defiance and protective instincts were demonstrated in the face of threats to her family and home. By taking such a courageous stance against intruders, she demonstrates a spirit of resistance against oppression. The sacrifice of Seetha represents the personal cost of fighting for justice and freedom.

Kamala is the sister of Veerareddy. It is evident that she is a proactive supporter of change. Kamala is an active participant in the revolution and the Sangham. She exhibits courage in defending her family's rights against oppressive forces. Through her assertive actions, she has demonstrated an unwavering commitment to social justice. Her resilience against adversity underscores the transformative power of individuals in confronting systemic injustices and advocating for collective liberation.

Ameen works as a police officer. He aligned himself with Jagannadhareddy. He is complicit in the oppression of revolutionary people, and he enforces the oppressive rules of Jagannadhareddy. He attempts to influence the Muslim community against Veerareddy and the Sangham at one point. During a conflict at Veerareddy's house, he physically violates villagers and shoots Seetha and Dadasaheb.

Dadasaheb is a farmer from the Muslim community. He plays

an important role in the revolution. Against Jagannadhareddy's oppression, he actively supports the Sangham and Veerareddy. Dadasaheb rejects joining Ameen, when Ameen plays religion politics, and when Ameen tries to separate him from The Sangham. He protects Kamala and Seetha during the confrontation with Jagannadhareddy's forces at Veerareddy's house. He dies during this confrontation.

Subhan is the brother of Mastan, but he does not support Mastan; instead, he actively opposes him. Subhan, a farmer from the village and a member of the Muslim community, aligns himself with Dadasaheb's principles. He holds a prominent position within the Sangham, where he plays an active role in organizing resistance against Jagannadhareddy's oppressive rule. Subhan courageously confronts Jagannadhareddy's unjust taxation policies and demands justice for the villagers. He advocates for unity within the village community and underscores the importance of collective action against exploitation.

Ramireddy, another farmer, assumes a significant role within the Sangham due to his strong leadership qualities. He directly confronts Jagannadhareddy's corruption and exploitation of village farmers, defending his fellow villagers against oppression.

Bandagi, a posthumous character, holds a profound connection to the

story. He is portrayed as an icon of revolution, having fought against injustice and oppression before being murdered by Jagannadhareddy's cohorts. Bandagi is depicted as a valiant warrior and immortal soul within the narrative. His tomb becomes a symbol of collective resistance against oppression, serving as an annual gathering place for commemorations and meetings.

4.2. Synopsis of the play:

Scene 1: The play unfolds at Bandagi's tomb, adorned with a basil plant, jasminum auriculatum, and other flowers. Subhan and Ramireddy stand together, while Veerareddy and Dadasaheb are seated nearby. Seetha and Kamala offer incense sticks at the tomb, followed by a song recounting Bandagi's sacrifices, clashes with Jagannadhareddy, and revolutionary legacy. Bandagi is portrayed as a warrior, an immortal soul, and a beacon of change in the song.

The tomb is surrounded by a large crowd of supporters, their enthusiasm for Bandagi's cause growing. Dadasaheb, Subhan, and Veerareddy discuss plans to revolt against Jagannadhareddy's injustice. Seetha comprehends the reasons behind Bandagi's revered status upon discovering Jagannadhareddy's oppressive tax system, while Kamala expresses her determination to join the revolution. Details emerge about Bandagi's murder, leading to hunger

and mourning among the villagers. Ramireddy then rallies the group against Jagannadhreddy's corruption, highlighting the villagers' suffering.

Following a discussion, Veerareddy, Subhan, and Dadasaheb plan to initiate a Sangham. Later, Ramireddy escorts Kamala and Seetha back to their home. Shortly after, Yellamanda arrives, furious after an altercation with Mastan, one of Jagannadhreddy's lackeys, over unjust taxation. Mastan then enters to inquire about the discussions at Badagi's tomb. Yellamanda and Mastan engage in another conflict, during which Veerareddy intervenes to break up the clash between them, leading to Mastan's departure. Mastan's rude behavior towards Yellamanda further fuels rebellion against Jagannadhreddy among the group. Subsequently, Ramireddy returns battered after confronting rowdies who had been harassing Kamala and Seetha on their way home. These rowdies are known to work for Jagannadhreddy, and this incident further inflames Veerareddy and his party with the spirit of revolt against Jagannadhreddy.

Scene 2: The scene unfolds in Jagannadhreddy's Diwanam, where Ramu, a servant, tidies up and arranges chairs and tables. Mastan enters, exchanging pleasantries with Ramu before Jagannadhreddy's arrival. When Jagannadhreddy appears, Mastan reports on people

visiting Bandagi's tomb, provoking Jagannadhreddy's anger. A police officer arrives, announcing Ameen's imminent arrival. When Ameen enters, Jagannadhreddy offers him the opportunity to stay at his home for the night, but Ameen declines. Jagannadhreddy then offers him a bribe, which Ameen reluctantly accepts. After consuming alcohol, Ameen hastily departs for Nalgonda.

Jagannadhreddy questions Venkatravu about villagers visiting Bandagi's tomb without his permission. Venkatravu reveals that the visits are clandestine. Mastan informs about an altercation with Yellamanda, leading Jagannadhreddy to command Mastan to bring Yellamanda before him. Venkatravu updates Jagannadhreddy on Veerareddy's activities, including the formation of a Sangham and the display of a revolutionary flag. Jagannadhreddy derides the Sangham members and instructs Ramudu to summon the village farmers to the Diwanam.

Yellamanda arrives, and Venkatravu questions him about the Gongallu offering owed to Jagannadhreddy. Yellamanda admits to providing only three out of the required five Gongallu, prompting Mastan to physically assault him due to his association with Veerareddy's Sangham. Venkatravu imposes a fine on Yellamanda for his Sangham affiliation and tries to coerce him

into admitting that he was pressured to join. When Yellamanda refuses, Jagannadhreddy commands Mastan to beat him until he complies, forcing Yellamanda to provide a finger impression on a white paper before being sent home.

Veerareddy, Subhan, and Ramireddy enter the Diwanam, where Venkatravu accuses them of failing to pay crop taxes and demands repayment of a debt owed by Subhan to Jagannadhreddy. Subhan explains his efforts to repay the debt, but Venkatravu questions his integrity and urges him to verify accounts with Veerareddy. Veerareddy argues against paying additional rice to Jagannadhreddy, highlighting the disparity in land ownership and tax responsibilities. Tensions escalate as both sides remain at odds, leaving the confrontation unresolved.

Scene 3: The scene opens at Veerareddy's home, where Kamala sings a lullaby to her nephew, son of Veerareddy and Seetha. Seetha enters, and she humorously debates Kamala's song choices, sparking a light-hearted discussion. Veerareddy teases Kamala about her song selection. During the conversation, Seetha brings up an incident where Kamala was teased while returning from Badagi's tomb. Concerned for Kamala's well-being, Seetha suggests arranging a marriage for Kamala. She believes that once Kamala is married and moves to her husband's house, it will keep her

away from this village and protect her from the rowdies' teasing. Seetha's viewpoint reflects traditional gender roles and highlights her reliance on male protection for women's safety. Seetha's assumptions about women confronting injustice are challenged by Veerareddy, who cites examples of women protesting military oppression. He emphasizes the importance of collective action by presenting Seetha with books from the Sangham. As they sing, they invoke heroic historical figures in a patriotic song.

The scene continues with the entry of Dadasaheb, Subhan and Yellamanda. Yellamanda shows his injuries, and he explains how he was beaten by Mastan and forced his thumbprint on a white paper. Ramireddy arrives and reports that Jagannadhreddy's people have forcefully taken his bullocks without his permission. Veerareddy also expresses grievances over the theft of Ramireddy's bullocks. Yellamanda further complains about Jagannadhreddy's people preventing his herd from grazing on government land. Veerareddy expresses frustration with the lack of proper governance and advocates for changing the government, seeking everyone's support for this. In response to Veerareddy's call for change, Yellamanda questions whether the Muslim community will support forming a new government against the current administration, given its

association with the Nizam's rule. Subhan asserts that the Muslim community does support this and challenges Jagannadhareddy's local governance by citing protests against injustice. During this discussion, Ramudu enters the scene.

Ramudu's visit exposes Jagannadhareddy's exploitative practices, including illegal land seizures, and Ramudu expresses a desire to join the Sangham. He also shares critical information that Dora and the Venkatravu have traveled to Nalgonda and plan to visit the city, leading the Veerareddy's people to suspect nefarious intentions such as framing them with false police cases. The scene concludes with the villagers reaffirming their commitment to the Sangham and singing a song. Throughout this scene, the villagers are depicted as resolute in their resistance to exploitation and oppression, emphasizing unity and empowerment through their struggles against injustice.

Scene 4: This scene begins with Jagannadhareddy and Venkatravu at Jagannadhareddy's home. They discuss strategies to undermine the spirit of the villagers who are joining Veerareddy's Sangam. Jagannadhareddy expresses confidence in his power and government support to suppress the villagers. Jagannadhareddy echoes this sentiment, boasting about the backing of one lakh soldiers from the

Nizam and claiming that, if needed, the British government will provide war tanks and aircraft to combat the villagers. He displays arrogance and dismissiveness towards the villagers and the Sangam, firmly believing that they are powerless against his strength and support.

Mastan enters with news that villagers collectively protested against working on Jagannadhareddy's farm and home, causing disruptions. Jagannadhareddy becomes further enraged by the shortage of labour. Ameen arrives, revealing complaints against Jagannadhareddy for alleged atrocities, but Jagannadhareddy and Venkatravu dismiss these as lies. The Venkatravu informs Ameen that villagers are disrespecting his authority by holding unauthorized meetings and swearing at the police, which enrages Ameen.

Initially sympathetic towards the villagers' complaints, listening to Jagannadhareddy's people, Ameen changes his mind. Now, Ameen aligns with Jagannadhareddy. Ameen takes his regular bribe from Jagannadhareddy. Ameen inquires about the leader of the Sangam, expressing surprise that Veerareddy, a member of Jagannadhareddy's clan, is involved in actions against him. They plan to divide and conquer by leveraging Muslim sentiment (Ameen's focus) and influencing the Reddy community (Jagannadhareddy's focus).

Mastan, Dadasaheb, and Subhan arrive. Before their arrival, Jagannadhareddy and the Venkatravu withdraw, leaving Ameen to address his clan. Upon their arrival, Ameen asks Mastan, Dadasaheb, and Subhan to sit, but they decline, indicating they are not interested in pleasantries. Ameen appeals to religious sentiments and questions their involvement in the Sangham, suggesting that Hindus are leading them astray from true Muslim values.

He promotes the benefits of aligning with the Nizam, emphasizing happiness and wealth. Ameen mentions the Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen, a Muslim organization offering benefits and respect, urging them to join this Sangham. Dadasaheb and Subhan strongly disagree, explaining that the Sangham supports the poor and oppressed regardless of religion, addressing the issues of all communities. They express hesitation to join the Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen, which they believe is controlled by landlords. Ameen warns them of consequences if they do not sever ties with the Sangham. Dadasaheb asserts they are not afraid and insist on remaining part of the Sangham before leaving. Jagannadhareddy and the Venkatravu return, learning of Ameen's failed attempt. They comfort Ameen, suggesting they persuade Veerareddy to cease his revolt against Jagannadhareddy. Ameen agrees

to rest, asking Jagannadhareddy to inform him of Veerareddy's response to their demands.

Now, Veerareddy arrives, he rejects Jagannadhareddy's offers of a government job and administrative role. Venkatravu becomes enraged and praises Jagannadhareddy's achievements, which Veerareddy challenges, accusing Jagannadhareddy of exploiting villagers for personal gain. The confrontation escalates as Jagannadhareddy insults Veerareddy, leading to a physical altercation where Veerareddy is forcefully restrained and arrested by Ameen on Jagannadhareddy's orders. This scene highlights the escalating tension between Jagannadhareddy's oppressive authority and the resistance led by Veerareddy and the Sangham, showcasing power dynamics and ideological clashes within the village.

Scene 5: The scene opens at Veerareddy's house where Seetha and Kamala are adorning icons of revolutionary leaders and freedom fighters with flower garlands. As they engage in this activity, Seetha sings a powerful revolutionary Telugu song conveying a message of empowerment and resistance against the oppression faced by farmers. The song emphasizes the principle that those who cultivate the land have rightful ownership over it and cautions against individuals who exploit farmers and their hard work. Overall, it advocates for a collective

uprising against oppressors who exploit and steal from farmers.

At the conclusion of the song, Dadasaheb and Subhan enter, inquiring about Veerareddy's whereabouts. Seetha informs them that he followed them to meet Jagannadhareddy, and Kamala adds that Ramudu came to inform them that Jagannadhareddy requested Veerareddy's presence, prompting him to go to Jagannadhareddy's house. Dadasaheb and Subhan ponder if Veerareddy might have taken a different route and missed meeting them along the way.

Soon after, Yellamanda enters in a jubilant mood, prompting Dadasaheb to question whether he had been drinking alcohol to be so happy. Yellamanda responds that he hadn't had a drop to drink since joining the Sangham, showcasing his commitment to responsibility. Dadasaheb wonders if Yellamanda's cheerful demeanor stems from catching his arch nemesis, Mastaan, but Yellamanda clarifies that this isn't the reason for his jubilation.

Ramireddy enters and extols Yellamanda's prowess with his shepherding crook. This piques everyone's curiosity, leading to inquiries about Yellamanda's recent actions and whom he confronted. Yellamanda, unable to contain his excitement, reveals that he imparted a significant lesson to Jagannadhareddy's people.

Ramireddy then recounts his sleepless nights, haunted by thoughts of his cherished bull seized by Jagannadhareddy's men. Eventually, he devised a plan and, with Yellamanda's assistance, intercepted Jagannadhareddy's flock at the lake, rescuing his bull and confronting Jagannadhareddy's people successfully. Yellamanda's crucial role in this victory brings joy to all, who commend Yellamanda and Ramireddy for their bravery.

However, the atmosphere shifted drastically when Ramudu arrived with distressing news that Veerareddy had been forcefully arrested at Jagannadhareddy's residence. This news dampened spirits, instilling tension and worry. Despite the formidable police presence at Jagannadhareddy's place, the group prepares to intervene, demonstrating unwavering resolve to fight for Veerareddy. Feeling pushed to their limits by Jagannadhareddy's oppressive rule, they vow to confront the situation fearlessly. Sita urges immediate action, emphasizing their history of hardship and the need to reclaim their freedom. Dadasaheb agrees to remain behind to protect Sita and Kamala, but Sita insists he secure his own family first, fearing their vulnerability should things escalate.

Ramireddy and Subhan urge everyone to divide and cover each street in the village to educate people about the current situation.

They emphasize the importance of gathering all villagers and preparing a defense. Seetha passionately urges them to fight until death, while Subhan delivers a compelling speech about their history of oppression and the need to reclaim their freedom. All individuals, except Seetha and Kamala, disperse to various houses to inform residents about the unfolding events, while Seetha and Kamala remain at home.

Seetha bids farewell to the departing villagers and anxiously surveys the surroundings, worried about the imminent threat. Kamala calls Seetha inside the home to prepare a plan to fight against Jagannadhareddy and his team in case they attack. Kamala shows a pot filled with dried chili peppers and a knife, outlining her strategy to blind their enemies with the peppers and subsequently eliminate them. Seetha endorses Kamala's plan, suggesting that Kamala hold their enemies' heads while she slits their throats with the knife. Concerned about her son's safety, Sita asks Kamala to protect him if anything happens to her during the altercation. Kamala reassures her, expressing confidence in their ability to face any challenge together.

Suddenly, a commotion erupts outside as Jagannadhareddy, accompanied by police, Ameen, and his goons along with Patwari, forcibly enters the house. Seetha blocks their entry, challenging their audacity to

invade her home. Ameen aggressively orders her to move, claiming they are seizing the house due to unpaid taxes. Jagannadhareddy's unsettling gaze on Kamala catches Sita's attention during the confrontation. Reacting swiftly, she confronts Jagannadhareddy and threatens to gouge out his eyes if he continues staring at Kamala. Enraged by her defiance, Ameen grabs Sita by her hair and throws her to the ground, cursing vehemently.

In the chaotic situation, Kamala attempts to attack Ameen, but Mastaan intervenes, blocking her and swiftly overpowering her in a brief scuffle. He then ties her hands while Venkatravu holds Sita down to prevent further disruption. Amidst the commotion, items are thrown out of the house while Sita vehemently protests their actions. In a moment of respite, Kamala manages to free herself and quickly grabs chili pepper from her pot, throwing it into the eyes of Jagannadhareddy's people. This unexpected move leaves them struggling with impaired vision and intense discomfort. Taking advantage of this distraction, Sita and Kamala retaliate by physically attacking Jagannadhareddy's people.

As the chaos intensifies, Dadasaheb enters the scene and witnesses the violence against the women, prompting him to react angrily by physically assaulting the perpetrators and admonishing them for their actions. Ameen, regaining

his vision and realizing that their side is losing control, retrieves his gun and shoots Dadasaheb and Seetha. With both individuals collapsing to the ground, Kamala, understanding the gravity of the situation, rushes to their aid in tears, seeking help. Observing the villagers closing in, Jagannadhareddy and his associates decide to flee the scene. Meanwhile, Veerareddy and Ramudu arrive at the house, discovering the aftermath of the violence. It becomes apparent that Dadasaheb has succumbed to the gunshot wound, while Seetha is in critical condition. Seetha, in a desperate state, entrusts Kamala with the responsibility of caring for her infant son before the scene concludes.

Scene 6: The scene opens at the graves of Seetha and Dadasaheb. Veerareddy, Subhan, Kamala, and Ramudu sing a song praising the bravery of Seetha and Dadasaheb.

Veerareddy and the other villagers blame Jagannadhareddy and his followers for killing Seetha and Dadasaheb. The discussion then turns to retribution, with talk of possibly burying Jagannadhareddy alive. Ramudu expresses unforgiving intentions towards Jagannadhareddy. Everyone emphasizes their determination to ensure justice for Seetha and Dadasaheb.

Ramireddy and the villagers enter with the arrested Venktravu. Venktravu pleads for forgiveness for his deeds and expresses

remorse, acknowledging his crimes. Subsequently, Yellamanda and the villagers bring Mastan, who is also arrested.

Yellamanda presents Mastan, highlighting his offenses and expressing shame towards him. Yellamanda explains Jagannadhareddy and Ameen's escape to the dissatisfied villagers who regret not capturing Jagannadhareddy. Kamala is tasked with reclaiming Jagannadhareddy's lands.

With Ramudu and Ramireddy expressing hope for the future and their determination to ward off adversaries, Ramudu suggests enlightenment and reclaiming their land. As they chant victory for the Sangham, symbolizing unity and resolve, they pledge to secure the farmlands of Seetha and Dadasaheb.

The play's ending song emphasizes stewardship of the earth and empowers women with a sense of patriotism. It questions land ownership and property rights, stressing the importance of collective duty and ethical stewardship in protecting the nation and its resources for future generations. The song inspires preservation and nurturing of the homeland through poignant language.

4.3. Feminist Themes in 'Maa Bhoomi':

In the play, female characters, Seetha and Kamala, are actively engaged in the movement aiming to overthrow

oppression. They challenge traditional gender roles, symbolizing endurance, strength, resilience, and determination. The first spirit of revolution is evident in the play's opening scene when Kamala and Seetha offer incense sticks at Bandagi's tomb, indicating their respect for revolutionary essence. Kamala demonstrates a spirited attitude towards revolution right from the outset, while Seetha undergoes a transformative journey as the play progresses. Initially, Seetha adheres to traditional gender norms, holding the belief that women depend on male protection for safety. However, she changes her perspective when Veerareddy recounts the violent protests of women against military oppression in Mallareddygudem. This shift in Seetha's perspective indicates women's capability to stand up against injustice.

The play also embeds issues of women's safety and resistance to oppression. For example, the play raises concerns about women's safety in scenes 1 and 5. In scene 1, Seetha and Kamala face sexual harassment while returning from Bandagi's tomb, highlighting the challenges women face under an oppressive government. Here, a lackey of Jagannadhareddy makes sexual comments towards Seetha and Kamala, but Ramireddy intervenes to protect them. Gender inequality and political oppression are evident in scene 5 when Jagannadhareddy's people confront

Kamala and Seetha. In this scene, they physically abuse them, and Ameen even shoots Seetha with his gun. Jagannadhareddy exploits the physical vulnerability of women, knowing they lack the strength to defend themselves, which leads to their abuse. Despite this, Seetha and Kamala, without seeking help from men, courageously fight against Jagannadhareddy and his people. Thus, the play vividly depicts women's struggle against political oppression and inequality under Jagannadhareddy's governance.

In the era depicted in the play, women were restricted from participating in pursuits beyond domestic responsibilities. However, in defiance of societal conventions, the play recognizes women's voices in catalysing social transformation. Kamala takes an active role in the revolution, she demonstrates a willingness to fight against injustices, and she inspires others to join the Sangham. Her active contribution demonstrates women's role in engaging with social issues. Kamala also deeply engages with literature centred on revolutionary themes. This engagement with the literature highlights her ideological progression. Kamala's revolutionary path signifies women establishing their own identities. Along with her brother, Kamala influences Seetha to immerse more deeply in revolutionary literature. This indicates Kamala's deliberate effort

to expand Seetha’s perspectives. This exemplifies women’s solidarity and collaborative intellectual engagement. Assisted by Kamala and Veerareddy, Seetha undergoes a significant transformation towards embracing empowered roles for women in political and social contexts. This collaboration emphasizes the “collective effort” to empower women in navigating political and social terrain. Seetha's transformation towards revolution does not compromise her responsibilities in caring for her family. This balanced approach, which involves managing both familial responsibilities and revolutionary activities, suggests a challenge to conventional gender roles.

Kamala sings a variety of songs, including lullabies, patriotic tunes, and revolutionary anthems. Her passion for diverse songs and singing reflects Kamala’s cultural connection and her efforts to uplift her community. Her engagement with these songs represents artistic expression, women's empowerment, identity, and the questioning of gender stereotypes. Kamala's dedication to singing revolutionary songs and teaching Seetha reflects her agency in expressing herself through music. This engagement not only inspires revolutionary ideas but also suggests women's empowerment through creative expression. Kamala doesn't just sing at home; she even sings

at Bandagi’s tomb. This challenges traditional gender roles that restrict women’s participation in public discourse and counters stereotypes about women's roles, educating people to change their notion that women's contributions should be limited to domestic roles. This also highlights Kamala’s capacity for intellectual and artistic pursuits. Overall, her engagement with these songs enriches the narrative and signifies women's agency in shaping political landscapes.

In Scene 3, Seetha and Kamala sing a song about historical women figures such as Jhansi Lakshmi Bai and Rani Rudrama Devi. This song directly portrays women as courageous, strong, and proficient leaders. It emphasizes the significant historical contributions of women, presents women as proactive participants in revolutionary movements of resistance, challenges societal perceptions of the capabilities of women, and advocates for gender equality. The participation of Kamala and Seetha in these revolutionary songs alongside men highlights the inclusive nature of the movement and positions women as equal partners in the revolution.

Scene 5 demonstrates the dynamics of power, resistance, and the roles of women in challenging oppression and violence. This scene is evident of women’s collective actions, challenging patriarchal authority, resisting aggression, showing

solidarity, support, vulnerability, and resilience. In this scene, Kamala and Seetha establish a fight against the oppressive forces of Jagannadhareddy. Kamala devises a plan to use chili peppers and a knife for self-defense, showcasing her determination to protect herself and her family. Despite the risks involved, Seetha confronts Jagannadhareddy and Ameen, displaying her courage in defiance of male-dominated authority and her steadfast opposition to oppression. The collaboration of Kamala and Seetha in this scene illustrates the significance of female solidarity in confronting violence and oppression perpetuated by patriarchal societal structures.

At the end of this scene, Seetha, in a desperate state, entrusts Kamala with the responsibility of caring for her infant son. Here, Kamala's commitment to protect the baby exemplifies solidarity and mutual care among the women. This bond underscores the significance of women providing mutual support during challenging circumstances.

In the final scene, Kamala expresses her anger and desire for punishment towards Venkatravu for his misdeeds against poor people. The anger she demonstrates is a shared sentiment within the community towards those who collaborated with Jagannadhareddy's oppressive administration. She demands accountability from Venkatravu

for his involvement in instigating Jagannadhareddy's actions against the villagers. Her efforts here, including advocacy for land reclamation, challenge traditional patriarchal norms that typically confine women to domestic roles. In this scene, women's sacrifice is honored. The scene centers around the commemoration of the sacrifices made by Seetha and Dadasaheb. Veerareddy and his comrades celebrate and commemorate the sacrifices made by Seetha and Dadasaheb in their pursuit of freedom and justice. It emphasizes their roles as courageous individuals who fought for justice, freedom, and social change. Others in the scene acknowledge the significant contribution of women against oppression, like Seetha, by celebrating the bravery and dedication of Seetha and Dadasaheb.

5. Conclusion:

The play "Maa Bhoomi" stands as a significant embodiment of the convergence of social activism, leftist politics, and cultural expression. The aim of this research paper is to analyse feminist themes within the play "Maa Bhoomi". From a feminist perspective, this research illuminates the nuanced roles and contributions of female characters within the socio-political environment portrayed in the play.

The discussion section introduces the characters and provides a synopsis of the play. Subsequently, the analysis

explores feminist themes, emphasizing the transformation of Seetha and Kamala as they transition from traditional gender roles to assertive defiance. Within the discussion of feminist themes, the paper emphasizes the significant role of education in empowering women, presenting the narrative of female empowerment within the context of the revolutionary movement. Additionally, the paper provides evidence of women's unity and identifies their indispensable role in the revolutionary movement for social change.

Furthermore, the paper observes the potential for women to challenge patriarchal norms and emphasizes the broader societal obstacles experienced by women, including issues of safety and political oppression. The research underscores the significance of female solidarity and reciprocal support in addressing social injustices.

In essence, "Maa Bhoomi" represents a significant cultural milestone in Telugu theatre, offering a perspective for exploring the diverse roles of women in shaping historical narratives and advocating for societal transformation. This feminist interpretation highlights the lasting significance of the play, stimulating ongoing dialogue on gender dynamics, resistance, and the pursuit of justice within the broader discourse of social and political change.

Glossary:

- i Sangham refers to a revolutionary movement and coalition in rural Telangana during the mid-20th century, particularly associated with communist ideology and the efforts to challenge feudal socio-economic structures (Purushotham, 2021 pp. 187-193). The Sangham aimed to bring about significant social, economic, and political changes, including the abolition of caste-based discrimination and labour, cancellation of debts, redistribution of land, and empowerment of marginalized groups such as landless laborers and women. The sangham's activities extended to cultural and educational initiatives aimed at spreading revolutionary ideas and mobilizing the rural population towards a vision of social justice and equality.
- ii Diwanamu" can refer to a court, administrative council, or royal chamber that played a crucial role in governance and administration. In the context of Maa Bhoomi, "Diwanamu" represents the court for governance, typically established within Jagannadhareddy's residence.

iii Gongali" indeed refers to a course woollen sheet used for warmth in Telangana. The term "gognallu" is used for the plural form of "gongali" in the Telugu language, commonly spoken in Telangana. These sheets are valued for their insulating properties and are popular during colder months to provide comfort and warmth.

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